

Teachers' and students' perceptions and practices in promoting a sense of community for blended education

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ABSTRACT

Blended learning is not a new concept, but has attracted increased interest among higher education institutions in preparing for future education. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many teachers have gained extensive experience with online and digital education. Yet, maintaining social engagement amongst and with students, while motivating them to actively participate in their learning, remains a momentous challenge for teachers working in a blended learning environment [1]. Poor social interactions cause a negative impact on the quality of blended learning [2], culminating in students feeling lonely, isolated, and losing motivation [3].

As such, a sense of community will be crucial, but may be difficult to achieve due to limited physical classroom time. This study addresses students' and teachers'

viewpoints, and seeks to answer the question: *What are the perceptions and practices of students and teachers regarding promoting a sense of community in a blended learning environment?*

A qualitative methodology is utilized, including non-participant observation, document analysis, and interviews for data collection and analysis. Firstly, the findings of this study enhance our understanding of teachers' perceptions, practices, and challenges for cultivating SoC. Secondly, this study provides information for professional development of teachers that carry out blended education. Finally, we hope this study can support higher education institutions in preparing and reshaping for the future.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Blended learning challenges

Blended learning (BL) has gained considerable attention in higher education for more than two decades [2]. Research suggests that BL has the potential to increase learning flexibility, accommodate individual needs, and improve student results [4, 5]. Combining the advantages of online education, while still including face-to-face contact, BL has attracted increased interest among universities in preparing for education post-COVID-19. However, teaching during the pandemic revealed that maintaining social connections with students and motivating them to learn was difficult [1]. This confirms previous research indicating that poor social interactions can lead to students' feelings of loneliness, isolation, and motivation loss [1, 3]. In this situation, a sense of community (SoC) is essential, representing 'a feeling that members have of belonging, a feeling that members matter to one another and to the group, and a shared faith that members' needs will be met through their commitment to be together' [6, 7].

SoC has a beneficial effect on learning. However, it can pose certain challenges in a blended environment. Hence, this study aims to investigate students' and teachers' perceptions and practices in promoting SoC, to gain insights on how to support students and teachers for a quality BL in higher education. More specifically, this study seeks to answer the following question:

What are the perceptions and practices of students and teachers regarding promoting SoC in a blended learning environment?

1.2 Theoretical background

Blended learning

Alongside ongoing debates regarding the best definition of BL, two definitions from Graham [8] and Garrison and Kanuka [9] are most frequently cited in various literature. Graham [8] considers BL as a mix of traditional face to face (F2F) and online learning. Similarly, Garrison and Kanuka [9] acknowledge that the essential

components of BL are F2F and online instruction or learning, and they further emphasize the importance of a *'thoughtful integration.'*

Sense of community in Blended learning

Despite BL's potential to improve the pedagogical richness and learning outcomes, some researchers have contended that it can be a double-edged sword if the social aspect in BL is overlooked. Learning is most effective when a strong sense of community exists [7]. Evidence suggests that SoC is associated with increased perceived learning, academic success, as well as students' well-being [7, 10].

SoC conducive to learning is important for the educational process, but it may be difficult to achieve, notably when physical classroom time decreases in BL. It is recommended for teachers to explicitly integrate SoC into both synchronous and asynchronous environments. To assist teachers in this area, Rovai [11] identified two critical variables to establish a strong SoC in BL: *connectedness* and *learning*. The connectedness refers to 'connectedness, cohesion, spirit, trust, and interdependence', while the learning focuses on the extent to which students impart educational goals and benefits through interaction with peers and teachers. Studies have further revealed that in order to build a strong SoC, three presences in BL are beneficial, namely: social and cognitive presence by students, and teaching presence [12-15].

- The ability of the students to project themselves socially and emotionally, as 'real' persons to develop inter-personal relationships in a trustworthy environment, is known as **Social Presence** [16]. Social presence contributes to the dimension of 'being connected' of SoC.
- Simply having good social relationships would not be sufficient for academic success. Interactive activities need to be structured and directed towards intellectual engagement. For this, **Cognitive Presence** becomes imperative. Cognitive presence is conceptualized as the extent to which the students are able to construct and confirm meaning through sustained reflections and discourse [17]. Cognitive presence focuses on the learning aspect of SoC.
- Teaching presence is the instruction, facilitation, and direction of students' social and cognitive presence for the purpose of realizing personally meaningful and educationally worthwhile learning outcomes [18]. Teaching presence is usually under the leadership of teachers and it is intertwined with social and cognitive presence to create a deep and meaningful learning experience for students [18, 19].

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research framework

An effective SoC that encourages connectedness and learning is fostered by well-designed and organized interactive activities spearheaded by teachers. These activities are characterized as social, cognitive, and teaching presence. In this sense, the three presences serve as this study's interpretive lens, analyzing students' and teachers' perceptions of SoC-promoting activities (see the Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework

2.2 Data collection and analysis

The university's ethics committee approved this study prior to data collection. Each participant was provided with a consent form and an information sheet regarding this study's aims, potential risks, and the option to withdraw from this study at any time. A blended course at one university was included in this study. This course was chosen as a sample for this study because it was developed over several years and complies with the requirements for a blended course as 'a thoughtful integration' of the F2F and online components [8, 9]. Additionally, the teacher of this course would like to investigate ways to improve students' SoC and interactivity, which would allow for a more in-depth examination of the course. The data collection spanned two phases: observation and document analysis were performed first, which provided input, directions, and knowledge to inform the interview questions in phase two, enabling a exploration of the participants' perceptions and practices on SoC.

- First, nine observation including both online and F2F sessions were scheduled at the beginning, middle, and end of the course, to explore SoC at various stages of the course.
- Secondly, this study obtained permission from teachers to access their courses via the learning management system (LMS). It scanned the course contents, assignments, and assessments and discovered specific course elements influencing students' SoC.
- Finally, one-on-one interviews with teachers and a group interview including five students have been conducted. The interview with the teacher provided

their perspective on their roles, teaching practices and their challenges in promoting SoC in BL. Interviews with students also revealed activities that would have contributed to SoC but were not supported by teachers.

The interview transcripts and the observation and document review notes served as the content analysis sources. The study generated two sets of codes to identify significant themes that would explain the perspectives of students and teachers on SoC. It utilized the pre-defined codes using the three presence categories and indicators [20]; while it established emergent codes by scanning obtained data to generate discoveries.

3 RESULTS

Although the study is still ongoing and the results are not yet fully available, preliminary findings indicate that specific pedagogical methods, practices, and tools that promote SoC in the BL environment can already be identified:

- A high-quality BL course requires teachers to consider students' social, emotional, and intellectual needs. A safe and open culture can be established by allowing students to express themselves without fear of repercussions.
- While it is easier to establish social bonds at the start of a course in a face-to-face session through icebreaker activities, teachers and students must work together to maintain them throughout the entire course.
- Personalize a BL course by including relevant personal stories, experiences, and examples. A video introduction with audio and video feedback are viable methods for boosting social presence. This strategy may encourage students to communicate their thoughts, feelings, and difficulties.
- Convert a static BL course into an active one with multiple opportunities for student engagement. Asynchronous activities (e.g., self-study and individual assignments) provide students with greater flexibility and control over their learning; on the other hand, synchronous activities encourage immediate personal engagement and more responsive exchanges (e.g., brainstorming, discussion, and live polling).
- Create an environment conducive to collaboration and encourage students to assist one another. It necessitates a shift in teachers' roles 'from sage on the stage to guide on the side' [21] by allowing students to assist one another first and then stepping in when necessary.

Additionally, this study shows that many universities are now required to offer hybrid education to allow corona-infected students to participate in online education. However, catering to online and on-campus students simultaneously is not easy; activities that should take place on campus (e.g., group projects) are forced to be moved online, raising concerns about the university's educational quality. It is important to stress that hybrid education is not synonymous with blended education. Universities should transition from emergency remote teaching to quality education by making well-considered decisions about which activities should take place online while others are better supported by F2F instruction.

4 CONCLUSION

Quality blended learning requires that students have a strong sense of community in order to keep them engaged and motivated throughout the learning process. Teachers play a crucial role in this process by imparting knowledge and fostering a safe and productive learning environment for students.

Furthermore, we hope that the study's future findings will identify the barriers teachers face and the support they require to develop a high-quality BL. We anticipate that this study will shed light on future professional development opportunities in blended education at HEIs.

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